

Finding, Using and Co-Designing Open Educational Resources: A Model for a Facilitated Communication on Shared Resources

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Abstract

This paper raises the issue of the rather vague definition of Open Educational Resources (OER) in respect to their educational features (“E”), and proposes a model for naming and describing the granularity, readiness to use and multiple parts and processes in the (co-)design, adaptation and redistribution of OER. The “openness” of OERs raises a new complexity in design, use and handing over learning environments, specifically related to the possibility of retrieving, adapting and modifying it, including re-use with different purposes. This cooperative work across the web and through OERs, mainly without direct interaction, produces numerous variants of the original OER, and raises risks of misunderstandings, both on what the OER is about - when searching for a specific resource – and on its appropriate use in education.

By clarifying the technical vocabulary and integrating fundamental dimensions for describing OERs, the model presented in this paper aims at providing a useful reference for facilitating the identification and communication about OERs in collaborative teams, and more broadly across researchers, designers and users. It also encourages a more precise design and description of OER, and invites readers to contribute to further develop the model presented here.

Keywords

Implementation; Half-baked; OER; Pedagogical Design; Teaching Device.

Graphical abstract

1. Introduction

Engaged with numerous partners in a research project aiming at the development of skills associated with the conception, the creation, and the implementation of Open Education Ressources (OERs) and Open Education Platforms (OEPs) (Gillet, 2020), I found myself faced with questions raised by the need for sharing and co-designing free and accessible numeric resources for teachers, students and pupils.

Firstly, the diversity of resources considered as OER by the partners and in the literature, raised the question of what exactly is an OER. UNESCO's definition to

introduce the concept in 2002 aimed at promoting and fostering a culture of sharing resources in education worldwide :

Emphasizing that the term Open Educational Resources (OER) was coined at UNESCO's 2002 Forum on Open Courseware and designates "teaching, learning and research materials in any medium, digital or otherwise, that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions. Open licensing is built within the existing framework of intellectual property rights as defined by relevant international conventions and respects the authorship of the work" (UNESCO, 2012).

However, this definition focuses on the open licensing, freely accessible numeric resources, stating little about the "E" in OER: educational resources are referred to as "material" without any consideration on formats, pedagogy, or the global coherency of structures like *modules* or *teaching sequences*. As recently pointed out for MOOC, the question emerges: "does one size fit all?" (Kolling, Weinberger & Niegemann, 2022, p. 25). For instance, the authors make the difference between xMOOC and cMOOC in order to help co-designers, users and researchers to find their way throughout the diversity of available formats. In this paper, we will start by discussing further the definition of OER for the same purpose.

Why is the matter of definition so important? The authors pinpoint the challenge of mutual understanding in co-design:

« However, co-design is still relatively new and there are significant challenges to the approach. Among these challenges is facilitating co-design in such a way as to promote the development of **a shared vision and mutual understanding** among the varied experts (Penuel et al., 2007). » (Kolling, Weinberger & Niegemann, 2022, p. 25, emphasis added by the author)

While the authors pursue this goal by presenting a model for the *process of co-designing* (called “CoDe-Graph”), this paper focuses on a complementary aspect: I present a model for *describing OERs as pedagogical devices*. This model is meant to support the co-design process, by facilitating the mutual understanding. For Dichev & Dicheva (2012, p.620), “the most problematic is the “finding-getting-using” challenge faced by educators seeking open content”. The fine description of an OER is indeed related to resources being “open”, since facilitating mutual understanding during the design with a common technical language, and the OER description when it is shared, may improve accessibility by specifying a particular OER across various types, formats, audiences, functions, etc.. One of the chief problem of accessibility concerns the communication, identification of the various nature of OER, as pointed out by Dichev & Dicheva (2012, p.619): “while the open content grows in popularity and we witness the proliferation of repositories and portals for OER content, it becomes more difficult for potential users to find the content they need.”.

Why would a model for describing OER help in this matter? From the perspective of work study, the use of ICT is long known to require structure and guidance (Postholm, Pettersson, Gudmundsdottir & Flem, 2004). Moreover, the possibilities OERs open, of sharing, modifying and re-creating open educational resources prepared by others, raise specific challenges in terms of cooperation (Lambolez & Perret-Clermont, 2004): when designing or creating educational resources in a cooperative or collaborative manner, or adapting or modifying an existing OER retrieved from an unknown author, the process may alter the educational quality or functions, even if the intentions are to adapt it to one's own context, or even to improve it. Since such cooperation remains remote in time and space, most often “speechless” – in the sense there are no interaction between the designers apart from the one through

the retrieving and modifying of the OER - it requires a particularly clear description for transferring intended information and meaning while avoiding potential misunderstanding (Perret-Clermont, 1992 ; Kohler, 2015).. For instance, Karlgren & Ramberg (2012) show in their study that ‘explicitly referring to design patterns by their names’ (p.231) was decisive for overcoming difficulties in collaborative design (‘co-design’).

Hence, this paper may contribute to facilitate co-design and accessibility of OERs by setting a vocabulary addressing the various features of educational devices, in a similar fashion Leblanc et al. (2008) propose for *instruments*. It may also facilitate exchange and dialogue among various types of professionals, supporting their cooperation. Such facilitation holds a promising potential for improving teaching and learning through the “reuse, redistribution, revision, and remix” of OERs, as Lin & Tang put it (2017, p.110), which they illustrate with their study on the adoption of OERs for coping with statistics anxiety.

In this sense, this paper address some of the UNESCO (2012) objectives, in particular :

Support capacity building for the sustainable development of quality learning materials.

Support institutions, train and motivate teachers and other personnel to produce and share high-quality, accessible educational resources, taking into account local needs and the full diversity of learners. Promote quality assurance and peer review of OER. Encourage the development of mechanisms for the assessment and certification of learning outcomes achieved through OER. (*idem*, p.2)

and:

Facilitate finding, retrieving and sharing of OER.

Encourage the development of user-friendly tools to locate and retrieve OER that are specific and relevant to particular needs. Adopt appropriate open standards to ensure interoperability and to facilitate the use of OER in diverse media. (*ibidem*).

2. Defining OER

2.1 *The Need of Disambiguation*

Despite existing for two decades, OER still need a precise definition according to Hoosen & Butcher (2019). The authors pinpoint overlapping with other concepts, OERs being sometimes confused with any Open Access content. For the authors, “OA can be used as OER if the open content is used in a teaching/learning context”. On the other side, not every teaching or learning resources qualify as OER: MOOCs, for instance, are not necessarily OERs, although a single MOOC may be, if under Open License and fully digitally accessible without any paywall. Hoosen & Butcher (2019) suggest to forgo any sharp distinction to what *is*, or *is not*, an OER : “some respondents do see MOOCs and OER on a continuum, which suggests a fluidity in ideas of ‘open’.” (*idem*, p.11). Atkins et al. (2007) reach the same conclusion: ““Openness” is complex and not a black-and-white issue—a spectrum of degrees of resource openness is developing. The future holds opportunities and challenges for enriching and exploiting this spectrum.” (p.28).

Although it may seem provocative, we will address a first and very basic question an OER user encounters when facing a website, an app on smartphone, or maybe an ebook: What is it?

In a frequently cited definition by the Hewlett Foundation's report, OERs “include full courses, course materials, modules, textbooks, streaming videos, tests, software, and any other tools, materials, or techniques used to support access to knowledge.” (Atkins,

Seely, Brown & Hammond, 2007, p.4). Such definition sounds like anything may account for an *educational* resources. Is that so?

For instance, if a school pupil visits Wikipedia for the first time, she may be wondering where she has to read it all, like a handbook section, memorize some elements - which ones? - or rather click here and there to be carried away, following personal interest. Is Wikipedia a teaching or a learning resources, in the sense mentioned in the OER definition? Is it merely a reference, as paper dictionaries and encyclopedia were intended? This type of questions have important pedagogical consequences. For example, in their study on design judgment in eLearning, Farmer & Koehler (2022) decided to simplify “the eLearning design process by providing a template teachers could use to efficiently “plug in” their content” (p. 6), which was based on Merrill's five Principles of Instruction (problem, activation, demonstration, activation, integration). As a consequence, the pedagogical creativity, diversity and freedom was considerably reduced in the design of the resources, restricted to a unique pedagogical approach. What if the teacher looking for an OER is precisely searching a different approach? More generally, the pedagogical content of OERs is often just considered “material” (see for instance UNESCO's definition), as if school activities could be retrieved and redistributed as isolated and unrelated parts without any mention or link to a structuring “sequence”. Yet, a specific activity or lesson could be precisely designed to follow another specific one, for making sense. If we are to interact and cooperate in designing teaching as coherent wholes, interrelated one to another, a precise description of what educational resources are, is needed.

2.2. *From the design of learning environment to OER*

Researchers have raised questions and issues about the design for teaching and learning for several decades already (e.g. Brown, 1992). Salomon (1996) raises the fundamental question: ‘What is the generic nature of the entities we call *learning environments*?’ (p.365). He considers the study of learning environments ‘difficult’, and ‘a challenging task’ (*ibidem*), and argues for a more comprehensive approach : ‘Salomon suggests that a new methodological framework is needed to evaluate the success of educational technologies – one that can use the entire learning environment as the unit of analysis, instead of attempting to isolate the effects of separate factors’ (Vosniadou, De Corte, Glaser & Mandl, 1996, p.8). Research literature is progressively moving the focus from the study of separable variables of learning environment, which are supposed to have specific cognitive effects on learners, to a study of educational settings as complex cultural wholes (Pressley & Roehring, 2003).

When defining OER further in details, Atkins et al. (2007) introduce “digital object” or “digital learning object” as “building blocks” (p.28):

We use “digital object” or “digital learning object” as the building block of the OER corpus. Digital objects can be recursive—a digital object consists of one or more digital (sub)objects. (Atkins, Seely Brown & Hammond, 2007, p.26)

The metaphor suggests that these are just piled up to constitute an OER. However, resources for teaching and learning are also designated in research literature as *learning systems*, or *pedagogical designs* (e.g. Lowyck, 2002¹). Concepts like

1 Lowyck (2002, p.199) defines *pedagogical design* this way : ‘Pedagogical design, a novel term in the conceptual landscape of instruction, teaching, learning and learning support, refers to any systematic choice and use of procedures, methods, prescriptions, and devices in order to bring about effective, efficient, and productive learning (e.g., Romiszowski, 1981).’

“system” or “designs” are used to refer to the links and organisational level constitutive of a whole. Are OER not constitutive of such wholes? Salomon answers in the affirmative by defining *learning environment* this way :

‘a composite of constituent factors: physical setting, set of agreed on behaviors, consensually held expectations and understandings, particular tasks, around prespecified contents for explicitly stated goals that are guided by a person who has been given the responsibility over that setting, its participants, and activities. In other words, a learning environment is first and foremost a *system* that consists of interrelated components that jointly affect learning in interaction with (but separately from) relevant individual and cultural differences (Salomon, 1991).’ (Salomon, 1996, p.365, emphasis added by the author)

As illustrated by this definition, the vocabulary for describing learning resources remains generally vague in educational sciences – despite existing precise concepts – mixing elements as different as *social norms* (Moscovici, 1984/1998), *tasks* (Leplat & Hoc, 1983), *objectives* (Bloom, 1956), *activities* (Halverson, 2002) and intentions.

Moreover, adjectives are often added to OER, such as *rich* (e.g. Miao, Mishra, & McGreal, 2016) or *computer-supported* and similar expressions are used to describe their content, such as *complex digital ressources (idem)*. All these terms refer to a set of resources and planned activities, including various formats – discursive, digital, multimodal, etc. – and scale. We would probably agree that a single worksheet cannot be considered a *learning*

environment as such – generally used for a more macro level of analysis – yet there is no established definition of the level

Granularity ↑	Wikipedia (unlimited)
	Full MOOC (6 month)
	Thematic Website (variable duration)
	One session e-learning (2 hours)

TABLE 1. *OER at various levels.*

of organisation, of complexity or of the quantity of resources, degree of support from computer, etc.

2.3 A matter of scale: Granularity

The problem of the unit – or granularity - has been raised by several authors in relation with the coherence within and across OER, for instance:

By granularity, we mean the size of the objects that can be individually tagged, referenced, found, and re-used under appropriated attached terms and conditions. Is the entire document the smallest accessible/usable object (not decomposable), or can one access and use sub-components such as images, videos, simulation applets, etc? By “object format diversity” we mean the diversity of representations and encodings of digital objects (often signified by a file name suffix: .pdf, for example) and how this diversity effects interoperability between digital objects composed into more complex objects. We are not advocating the adoption of a single standard, especially as this is unlikely to happen. We are, however, noting the importance of accommodating heterogeneity in service of coherence. (Atkins, Seely Brown & Hammond, 2007, p.26)

To introduce this issue of granularity, Figure 1 (below) represents a diversity of OER on this first dimension: educational resources can be classified on a continuum from the smallest units, such as a single teaching or learning session, to huge whole, such as the entire Wikipedia online encyclopedia. Of course, examples on Figure 1 are only illustrative and leave aside many questions, such as for instance : “where are the boundaries of an OER when related to external content on the web?”, “what is the adequate unit of measure for granularity, the duration needed for reading the content, for learning (as illustrated in Figure 1) or could we use the quantity of files or even Mbits?” and “should the duration be defined according to the users wishing to explore more or less in depth, or according to objectives, successful evaluation or even an intended curriculum?”.

This categorization of granularity could clarify the wide range of diversity in the designation of elements of OERs, we find in the literature: for Farmer & Koehler (2022) an OER is a single eLearning lesson, following a fixed template, while for Valle et al. (2018), a single OER contains over 30 lessons, notably including “questions, learning objectives, a video tutorial, a practice assessment with elaboration feedback, and in some cases, supplemental materials and video” and among which are “instructional packages” and “material”. Which includes which and what, becomes challenging to imagine.

2.4 A Starting Point: The Device

The term teaching *device*² is used here according to Weisser's definition :

Let us define a Device as the articulation of heterogeneous elements, material and symbolic (Charlier & Peter, 1999 ; Weisser, 2007) (...)

The Device is the virtual result, of a engineering work that foresees the semiotic or instrumental tools (Vygotski, 1930/1985 ; Mercier 1998) to make available to a subject for his relation to the world to become a source of learning' (Weisser, 2010, p.292, translated by the author)

The logical feature of the device merits to be stressed : a scattered set of resources does not constitute a device. It is only its ‘articulation’ - i.e. the logical relations or planned coordination of the subject's actions – that may constitute the whole and let it work as a system (of intentions and resources). Now, a device is not yet an actual teaching or learning system, since it only exists as a potential. To clarify this

2 This term is chosen here for translating in daily English the French concept *dispositif* d'enseignement, of which *dispositif* comes from the work of Foucault, and is particularly challenging to translate into English (Callewaert, 2017). Yet, terms as *learning system*, *pedagogical design* or *learning environment* may roughly refer to the same idea, depending on the actual author(s).

point, Weisser (2010) proposes a first distinction between *teaching device* and *learning situation* : ‘It is necessary to distinguish the mediating Device imagined by the teacher and the Situation that the learner later experiences, when the first is put into practice’ (*idem*, p.292, translated by the author). The experienced situation should not be confused with the *learning device* itself, as it is often the case while presenting the results of innovative ways of teaching or learning. Indeed, a single *learning device* may lead learners to very diverse experiences, depending on individuals, or on the context, etc. To stress only one classical example of this issue, let's imagine a class where pupils are interfering with the lesson through behavioral disorders, causing many interruptions. The way the learning device is experienced by pupils, even taken as a group (the collective experience of it) is likely to differ greatly from the way a peaceful and quiet group of pupils of the same age and characteristics could experience it.

This distinction between a device, that is prepared before the moment of teaching and learning – as *intentions* and *resources* – and the situation experienced by the students and the teacher is fundamental and generally agreed upon by researchers in educational sciences when explicitly enunciated. However, a *device* entails an additional feature compared to intentions only, as in a curriculum : the Latin root of *device* (*dispositif*) is both referring to an organisation – the logical feature mentioned above – and as a strategy, or even as a command. Within a device (*dispositif*), the teacher's intentions do not only take an organised form, yet equally constitute strategies (a detailed coordination of means and ends within a more or less hierarchical set) which have the function of commanding the envisaged practice. Any device is constructed with a foreseen practice in mind (Callewaert, 2017), otherwise it is irrelevant.

In addition to these fundamental distinctions, more can be said on the usage and appropriation of the device by the teachers and by the students. As underlined by Weisser (2010), each and every one ‘has his own way’ with a device³ :

Approaching human subject in an education vision rather than in a coercive one, leads us to take distance with the panoptic perspective dear to Foucault (1975) : the student learns from elements taken from the Device, yet he brings to the Situation a certain number of complements which are less controlled by the teacher, he ‘has its own way with it’. (*idem*, p.292).

This reasoning can be extended to teachers taking over a device for their own practice with one or several classes. Beyond Weisser's distinction between pedagogical device and didactical device, this paper also addresses the portential confusions resulting in the various forms and versions of a device, when it is taken over by someone else, shared or used multiple times, as it is so easily done with numeric resources. When sharing a device, however, it is more or less transformed: Used as a mean of communication, it is interpreted (slightly) differently by each actor, throughout the process of mediation constitutive of meaning making (Bruner, 1990).

2.5 Various of the Same: The Issue of Implementing and Re-creating OER

Educational sciences often do not distinguish between teaching as it is designed and planned, with specific resources, and its local specific adaptations (see for instance: Tiberghien, 1997; Grossen, Perret & Probst, 2007). In English, the concept of *implementation* falsely induces the idea that teaching may be identically reproduced throughout time and places, despite the specificities of each context (cultural background, curriculum, division and definition of teaching matters, etc.), change in teachers (pedagogical style, familiarity with the topic, numeric skills, etc.) and students

3 Translated from French: ‘y met du sien’.

(age, habits and usual learning strategies, previous learning gains, etc.). To the contrary, research shows that practitioners always adapt educational resources to their own objectives, context, understanding or even to their liking (see for instance: Sandoval & Bell, 2004). In their study, Dichev & Dicheva (2012, p.621) have 200 OER users in Computer Science (n=315) declaring to use them “by adapting it to fit my context”, while only 75 declare they (would) use them “as it is published”. Also, participants to this study mention “finding” and “customizing” OER the “most significant barriers” to their use, pointing notably “difference in the style and terminology used” (*ibidem*).

In order to address this issue, Kohler, Chabloz & Perret-Clermont (2015) borrowed the concept of “half-baked”⁴ devices from informatics, in which it refers to programming layers allowing to further develop many more baked variants of the software. This concept allows to represent the production of a great diversity of variants of a device, starting from a given educational resources, addressing explicitly the matter of adaption to their own practices, by teachers or any users, that may considerably transformed the taken over resources. OER are particularly concerned by this issue, since the “openness” directly aims at such takeover and production of many variants.

Figure 2 represents this second dimensions, with examples from Figure 1 classified in a way that illustrate the diversity, from a well-structured MOOC guiding learners closely but difficult to use in any different ways than planned, to the Wikipedia website that can be explored freely for learning on a topic or preparing a course, yet without any pedagogical guidance. This classification is merely illustrative, and does not imply every MOOC has a high readiness of use, of course, since it depends on the specific MOOC, its detailed content and quality.

4 Despite what might be suggested by the term “half” in the concept of *half-baked*, no assumption is made on the gradient of preparation of the device here, and “half” is merely a metaphor for “partially” and does not imply a precise middle or any proportion.

When consciously designed as *half-baked*, teaching devices are deliberately incomplete for some part or features (learning goals, classroom management, sequence in which tasks are distributed, etc), in order to leave a margin of

Granularity ↑	Wikipedia		
			Full MOOC
	Thematic Website		
		One session e-learning	
	Readiness to use →		

TABLE 2. More or less “baked” OER at various levels.

freedom and to invite professionals to collaborate around half-baked teaching devices (Chabloz & Kohler, 2021), more consciously adapting taken over educational resources to their own context, curriculum and audience.

When a teaching device is considered as complete as it can be before the actual teaching and learning, it becomes fully-baked. Yet, fully-baked teaching devices can still produce a diversity of versions or *variants*, yet the variations are not integrated into a designed margin of freedom, and thus may alter any element or feature of original teaching device, and interfere with the intentions of the design. In particular, Open Education Resources are meant to lead to the production of derivatives devices, which are precisely new versions released by users after adapting a (fully-baked) teaching device to their own practices.

In the presented Model, the various derivatives teaching devices and the various versions of half-baked devices will be referred to as *variants*. They have the following characteristics:

1. Variants embody the original teaching device, of which at least some elements or features can be found untouched or unmodified.
2. Variants bring diversity to the original device : choices have been made, modifications added and transformations operated that make the variant a unique and

specific device. More particularly, the variant may transform a teaching device into a learning device (see below).

The diversity resulting from personal adaptation of a teaching or learning device is obviously valuable, offering the necessary room and freedom for practitioners to exert their professional judgment on the relevance of specific elements of the design they take up for their particular class or students.

In addition to Weisser's (2010) distinction between *device* and experienced *situation*, the question to whom the OER is addressed – a crucial point in communication – leads to further distinctions: wherever the device is addressed to teachers – notably for providing relevant resources for teaching – or to students or pupils, for instance as an online module for self-regulated learning, or as a worksheet with specific instructions for guiding students throughout the various tasks. Let us call the first one a *teaching device* – like most school textbooks in which there are ‘pedagogical guidelines’ or even a ‘teacher's textbook’ – and the second a *learning device*, directly useable by learners without needing to be at school nor accompanied by a teacher. The learning device cannot be equated with the learning *situation*, since in a device teaching and learning are nothing but intentions: A learning device never guarantees the actual learning of who uses it. Following the example of studies on communicative intentions made in conversational pragmatics (e.g. Moeschler, 1985 ; Ghiglione & Trognon, 1993), such intentions are both together aiming at the transmission of informations (the ‘learning goals’ and ‘teaching goals’) and addressing a specific audience, all at one time on the form and on content.

The device, as a structured set of semiotic and material resources, only prepares to a communication process (or even to a cooperative process, see section 2.3). This is the reason why the distinction between a device addressed to teachers and a device

addressed to learners is particularly important: A well-prepared communication process entails knowing and adapting to the relevant audience (Perelman & Olbrechts-Tyteca, 1958/2000). Obviously, some device are hybrids, either addressing both teachers and learners in specifically designed sections, either addressing confusingly any type of user. In this last case, it goes as in any communication process: The risks for such devices to foster misunderstandings, inadequate usage or confusion is probably higher. For instance, a research (Kohler, 2023) shows that student's misconceptions in science, as described in a handbook intended for teachers, are misunderstood by the teacher when he transforms the handbook description into a school task, and consequently poses learning difficulties to his students. This study goes further, showing that some students' misconceptions in science are directly resulting from the way knowledge is communicated in the educational resource.

Kontopodis & Perret-Clermont (2016) propose to describe *learning environments* as 'interwoven socio-material ordering'. They also bring an interesting critique of the way research subjects have been treated, and advocate for the inclusion of the point of view of research participants, opening the field of study to the way learners experience by themselves the learning environments they encounter.

2.6 Taking into Account the Multiple Points of View

Who an OER is addressed to is also matter of great diversity. Considered *teaching* material by ones, it because *learning* material under the pen of others (Stansberry, 2017), or even *instructional* material (Valle & al., 2018). To give another example, the online *Glossary Of Education Reform*⁵ does not contain any specific term to define how to design teaching, before its implementation by a teacher. It contains the term *learning*

5 Great Schools Partnership (2013-2021). *The Glossary Of Education Reform*. Published online: www.edglossary.org.

environment, yet it has a much broader sense than in the previously quoted publications, including the whole context of teaching, even the local culture surrounding teaching and learning practices. Another technical term presented in the Glossary is *learning experience (idem)*, which clearly refers to the activity taking place rather than to the activity as it is designed. However, such *learning experience* does not distinguish between the points of view, while a student may experience the activity very differently from the teacher. This may lead to a confusion between teaching (intentions) and (effective) learning.

Such ambiguity often runs through the teaching and learning resources themselves : hence, a handbook may include both pedagogical advice for teachers and worksheets ready as they are for copying and distributing to students. To this ambiguity corresponds a great diversity of usages in school practices: while some teachers only ‘get inspired’ by a book, systematically designing their own activities or even their own documents, other teachers provide students with photocopied extracts of the same book, and follow scrupulously the book's model. However, there are no specific terms available to refer specifically to this diversity of functions and usages.

The matter of taken over education resources and their variants, raises the question of who the user is: for who is the resource considered more or less “ready to use”? While taking over content from Wikipedia for preparing a lesson on a topic may require an important load of work – it has a *low readiness* to be used *by a teacher* – it may be very easily accessible for a learner with a specific questions on a topic, for who the reading of (a part of) a page of Wikipedia may suffice for finding the sought answers – it has then a *high readiness* to be used *by a learner*.

TABLE 3. More or less “baked” OER at various levels, from two points of view.

Figure 3 presents the complexification of the Model taking into account these two points of view, stressing the possible – yet not systematic – change of classification in the *readiness of use* depending on its usage for *teaching* or rather for *learning*.

For instance, the relative rigidity given to a MOOC by its numeric embodiment may guide and limit both the learners' exploration and the teachers' use of it as a resources, while a well-documented session of teaching may be very easily handed-over from teachers to teachers, yet maybe not so easy to join in for students (depending notably on the quality of its pedagogical features). Here again, classification shown in Figure 3 are only illustrative of potential discrepancies between the points of view, since many configurations may appears depending on the actual OER under description. There is nevertheless a tendency for *low granularity* – educational resources with a high level of details – to be related to a *higher readiness* for teachers' use, since such details generally make them more “baked”.

In the next section, I present a Model supporting a more precise description of these educational features, and progressively introduce various dimensions to such description.

3. A Model for describing OER

3.1 Introducing the graphical Model

Now equipped with a few fundamental dimensions for describing educational resources, this section introduces the Model with Figure 4 (below), and the following sections where the choice of vocabulary and graphic representation is further explained.

Figure 4. A descriptive model.

The graphic synthesis of the Model (see Figure 1) can be approached from three angles, constituting three axes represented in red on the figure, which are structuring the whole :

1. Horizontally, the distinction between the points of view of the teachers and the point of view of the learners (axis x) makes it possible to distinguish between teaching and learning devices, between half-baked and fully-baked teaching devices, and between the various variants.
2. Vertically, the axis (y) represents the degree to which intentions are put into practice, starting with more or less precise objectives (on top of the figure) to the situations experienced by teachers and learners (represented at the bottom of the figure). Any device is designed on the ground of some type of objectives. Yet, what learners and teachers actually experience with the device differs for each individual. The situation represents the myriads of ways the overarching and unifying initial intentions are actually put into practice throughout the implementation of the device.
3. On the last axis (z), the multimodality of all the represented elements on the figure is suggested through a multiplicity of dimensions (material, semiotic, virtual, etc.). These ‘layers’ maintain complex interactions with each others – for instance the links learners are supposed to make between concrete situations, material resources, semiotic means, virtual environments, etc. – which can be part of the design (e.g. in a blended learning device) – or which may appear over time or through transformations operated on the device through several variants. In addition, some device may be available to all and everyone, shared on numeric platforms for instance, which is another interesting characteristic of the multimodality of teaching and learning devices.

3.2. *A few important Distinctions*

In addition to the description and characteristics of the devices, other components may benefit from precise distinctions, briefly discussed here below.

A *learning device* may be designed from the founding intentions, or may derivates from a (half-baked) teaching device, for instance as a secondary product of a teacher's adaptation of the device to his or her specific practice in class. A learning device may also take various shapes depending on the scale of its logical organization: A minima, a learning device is constituted of a single task, punctually devolved to any learner, without any coordination with other activities on his or her behalf. Beyond this minimal case, wholes of all sizes can be constituted, from one or more lesson(s), to bigger learning devices including several online modules interrelated through learning pathways, for instance. At most, a whole formation may constitute a learning device, or even a Website as huge as Wikipedia – but only if the key criteria of the logical coordination between the various elements of the device is respected. In this sens, Wikipedia is a learning device. However, a sum of isolated online courses may not constitute *a* device. In the same vein, the notion of learning sequence is relictively used, in this paper, to refer to a device sequentiality organized according to pedagogical principle. It is not used for refering to modular content and activities, or when tasks are proposed to learners without any overarching organisation. A sequentially organization may be a linear progression from easy tasks to difficult ones, from one theme to another, or may be opened to the learners' choices within a dynamically regulated form of sequentiality, as for exemple in customized learning pathways related to learning analytics. In this sense, Wikipedia may probably not be considered a learning *sequence*, given the absence of pedagogical guidance or tracking of the learner in the exploration of the encyclopa.

As each *situation* is perceived a different way by each singular participant, the vocabulary laid in this paper invites to distinguish rigorously the various points of view when referring to it: A situation is unique and univocal only relatively to one own's point of view (e.g. 'it was the time we made this and that...'), yet not as an *object of discourse*⁶, nor as an event or 'fact' to which one refers. The mere setting of (partially) shared experiences into an 'event' or a 'fact' entails, per definition, a certain degree of agreement among several points of view. At the moment in which a situation becomes an object of discourse, it becomes indispensable to specify the point of view we are referring to : For instance, the teaching situation could refer to the situation as it is seen by the teacher, or the way the teacher experiences the teaching activity. From the point of view of the pupils or learners, there are obviously as many situations as there are learners. However, an adequate methodology may also present a collective experience, albeit simplified, according to the principle of a partial convergence of all the various individual experiences (represented in figure 1 by the partly overlapping of colored areas).

3.3. A few important Processes

In addition to the components visible on Figure 4, some processes also are represented on the graphical model, allowing a precise designation.

The design or *designing* – the former may be less ambiguous than the latter for referring to a process – of teaching or learning devices actually entails several intertwined processes, some of which are creative (imagination, invention, innovation, etc.), while others are a concretisation of the intention (such as the ones we may find in a curriculum) and ideas (layout, choice of content, etc.), or operate a focalisation (a

6 See Peirce's semiotics or Grize (1996), for a definition of this concept.

specific focus or an outlook from the initial intentions, a selection among many possible ways of doing or throughout content, etc.).

Taking over a half-baked teaching device to make a fully-baked teaching device, may be designated as the *finishing* (like in industrial processes⁷), or as a specific type of *customization*, a notion widely spread in informatics which refers to the fine-grained or last layer choices made by the end-user for personal *motives*⁸, notably in order to adapt it to a context, or to local constraints. The transformation of a teaching device into a learning device is the expected *usage* of the former, since a teaching device remains ever an intention (of providing an adequate milieu for someone to learn something from it). Such process is distinguished, in Figure 4, from another one, often called *implementation*⁹, which leads from the intentions to some type of real activity, often evanescent when it comes to teaching and learning. This distinction is rarely made, and the various axes structuring the Figure 4 (see above) support its relevance: the usage is merely the passing from one point of view to another (generally from teacher to learners), while the implementation is the passing from intentions to an experienced reality. In literature, the distinction made in ergonomics between prescribed and actual tasks (see for instance Leplat & Hoc, 1983 ; Leutenegger, 2009) supports a cautious

7 According to the dictionary of the French Academy, the finishing (‘finissage’) is the ‘last phase of the making of an object’.

8 The Activity Theory (Leont'ev, 1975/1984) distinguishes between the culturally defined, institutionalized or official *aim* of an activity, often the one given by the designer if any, and the *motives* of the performer of the activity, who enters activity with his/her personal intentions.

9 It could also be called *actualization*, in order to stress the transformation from a planned to an actual practice of teaching and learning. We have preferred here the most widely used term.

examination of the implementation process, considered the various discrepancies between intentions and practice that can easily occur.

Within learning devices, an important process is the *regulation* of learning (evaluation, feed-backs, decision making about how to resume work, etc.). A distinction can be introduced wherever learners have or not a certain degree of autonomy for *self-regulating* their learning, including a margin of freedom for taking decisions (e.g. choosing tasks) and a sufficient power in the system. On the one hand, learners can have a complete self-regulation of learning, leaving them the freedom to set their own variant of the learning device. Wikipedia, if considered a learning device, would be at the extreme pole of self-regulated learning, since everyone is invited to explore the encyclopedia by clicking on the links as it pleases. On the other hand, a classical strict *heteroregulation* represents cases such as a regimented class performing tasks only when the teacher requires it, or setting a more or less constraining structure in which assessments must be succeeded before accessing new parts of the device. Obviously, all the variations between these two extremes exists, and are documented by research (see for instance Panadero, 2017). In numeric or hybrid learning devices, the heteroregulation can also be supported or even taken in charge by the software, which is gathering information (learning analytics) to either address it to teachers (support to an heteroregulation operated by the teacher), either to directly use it within the software for guiding learners accordingly (programmed heteroregulation) or for proposing tasks to learners (support to self-regulation). A similar diversity in the use of information about learners can be found in presential teaching in class, which often depends on a pedagogical style (e.g. *explicit teaching* is a type of programmed hetero-regulation, while *active pedagogy* is focused on increasing the part of self-regulation).

Within the global picture of the descriptive Model presented here, the supposed-to-be-known process of teaching takes a specific place, clarifying the precise work of teachers bringing the intentions and structuration of a teaching device into a situation experienced by herself or himself and by students in a way that matches the device's description, as much as it may. No wonder the professional act of teaching is often considered as an art rather than as technical or scientific knowledge: the model allows us to understand how much it has to do with a day-to-day performance.

Naturally, devices are designed within a cultural and historical *context*, with particularities in terms of education. Yet, their quality as a whole constituted of organized elements allows them to be (sometimes) usefull and relevant even out of the context in which they have been designed, be it for meeting the need of another context, or for producing variants locally adapted. Last but not least, sharing devices for cross-contextual use or implementation requires transmittable support such as books, printed worksheet or numerical data (websites, shared repositories of files, etc.). Since concrete and semiotic supports are more and more easily transformed from one modality to another (printing files, watching a video to prepare one's own discourse, 3D printers, etc.), *multimodal* devices should now be considered the norm rather than exceptional. Yet, each time a transformation occurs, more or less fundamental change are operated on the device, which raises challenging questions for research.

4. Perspectives for developping the Model

While remaining modest in scope – the model can be specified further in details – the model sketched in this paper nevertheless appears complex enough for individual appropriation. I am yet hoping it may serve as a mean for facilitating cooperation in design, development, use and share of Open Educational Resources. As pointed out by Dichev & Dicheva in their conclusions, “Just a great volume of open content is not

sufficient. It should come in a variety of depth, details, levels and grain-size.” (p.624): the Model proposed here allows much more precise answers to the few challenging question addressed in the beginning of the paper, as examples illustrating what a descriptive model may bring to the field:

- What type of OER am I looking at? For instance, is Wikipedia an OER ?
- Can I explore a MOOC on circular economy found on Internet and transpose it to make it my teaching sequence at college?

To the first question, the Model allow to a shaded answer: yes, in the sense of a *learning device* – one can learn a lot browsing the encyclopedia – yet without any teaching *sequences*, but not in the sense of a teaching device, since providing Wikipedia to someone does not constitute a teaching device. It could nevertheless play a role in teaching devices, in reference of specific activities where students are invited to use it to perform a task, or even as a source book for the teachers' own preparation on a topic.

To the second question, the model provide the key processes where knowledge will be transformed by the design of the teacher or creator of OER: *designing*, *customization*, *usage*, etc. Moreover, the obstacle a teacher may encounter in the reappropriation of the MOOC may be directly related to its *readiness to use* – if *fully-baked* it is more difficult to adapt it to a local context – and the choice made during the *designing* may be related to the *experience situations* of numerous learners.

More precision can still be added to this first version of a descriptive model, of course, and you are welcome to ameliorate it in your future publications, a an “open” model. Such model can provide a solution in order to “structuring OER metadata to tuning OER search engines” a need stressed by Dichev & Dicheva (p. 619).

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I have no competing interests to declare.

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